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Deliverable 2.10

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.10 overview

Marine Protected Area (MPA) networks are a cornerstone of marine conservation, yet their effectiveness hinges on their being appropriately located, ecologically representative, and effectively protected from human impacts. Climate change can also affect the distribution of species within MPA, raising questions about the ability of MPA networks to maintain both present-day ecological representivity and long-term resilience through climatic connectivity. Climatic resilience of the network can be studied using several measures. Here, we evaluate how ocean currents and projected climate velocities are mapped to an ecologically “Representative Biodiversity Area” (RBA) network for European seas. We modelled oceanographic connectivity using a decade of sea surface current data in a circuit theory framework to identify putative dispersal hubs and corridors. We assessed climatic connectivity by calculating climate velocity under a high-emissions scenario (SSP3-7.0) to map putative pathways for species range shifts. We then quantified the spatial overlap between these connectivity indicators and within the RBA. We found no significant difference from random connectivity within the RBA, indicating that sea surface connectivity will not change from the present within the RBA. However, the role of sea surface currents in the dispersal of species is not well understood. Other measures of connectivity, including genetic, habitat, and realised (present species distributions), need to be considered in the context of human impacts, including climate change. Assessment of climate resilience needs to consider not only connectivity, but the present distributions of species in macro- and micro- climate refugia, and species’ populations’ health and environmental tolerances.

Introduction

The ocean plays a critical role in climate regulation while supporting the food security and livelihoods of billions of people (Pörtner et al., 2022). However, it faces a severe and multifaceted threat from unsustainable fishing, pollution and other human activities. In addition, the climate crisis is causing significant disruption in the ocean through rising temperatures and extreme weather events, notably heatwaves (Allison & Bassett, 2015; Garrabou et al., 2022). These climate-driven pressures add to the existing stressors, including overfishing, unregulated coastal development, and plastic and chemical pollution, which collectively undermine the integrity of marine ecosystems (Gissi et al., 2021). In response, recent international agreements, including the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework's '30x30' target, have created a powerful mandate to expand Marine Protected Areas (MPA) (Watson et al., 2023).

Systematic conservation planning maximises the inclusion of as many species as possible in an MPA network by giving greater priority to areas with more geographically rare species. Thus, places with endemic and threatened species get higher priority. For example, islands distant from the mainland would be prioritised for protection because their endemic species could not be protected anywhere else, such as the Azores with 59 endemic marine species (Borges et al., 2010). Maintaining the ecological integrity of such areas is achieved by limiting the human introduction of species. However, there may be a risk that changing ocean currents and climatic conditions may also introduce species that may similarly compromise endemic species survival.

Europe's Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 - a core component of the European Green Deal - aims to establish a system of protected areas and restore damaged ecosystems (see e.g., Nature Restoration Regulation (European Commission, 2022)). Its targets for the land and ocean are similar: at least 30% of EU areas are to be protected, with one-third of those areas (10% overall) strictly protected (i.e., with no fishing or other harmful human impacts permitted) (Hermoso et al., 2022). Achieving these goals necessitates a scientifically robust framework to guide the placement of new protections, a challenge addressed by the MPA Europe project. This project is developing an ideal MPA network design for European waters, encompassing the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) of the Atlantic, Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas. It designed the optimal network using standardised species ranges of ~11,000 species, which are published on OBIS (Principe et al., 2023).

Population connectivity addresses the exchange of individuals between populations by the dispersal of life-stages by swimming, crawling, rafting, floating, hitchhiking, and the dispersal of larvae and other propagules on ocean currents (Shanks et al., 2003; Cowen & Sponaugle, 2009; Berkström et al., 2022). These processes maintain genetic diversity, aid population persistence, and allow protected areas to replenish themselves and the surrounding waters (Sève et al., 2023). The species within MPA also occur outside the MPA although the abundance, maximum body size and genetic diversity of some species may be less outside the MPA due to fishing and habitat variation (Costello & Connor, 2019). In contrast to protected areas on land, where landscape fragmentation due to urbanisation and farming isolates habitats and species' populations, only land and open ocean expanses over deep sea form physical barriers to marine species dispersal (Costello & Connor, 2019). This is evident by the expansion of thousands of marine species poleward under climate change globally (Chaudhary et al., 2021) and in Atlantic and Arctic European (Gordó-Vilsaeca et al., 2023a, b, 2024) seas. Within a generation, marine species can disperse tens to

hundreds of times further than terrestrial species (Kinlan & Gaines, 2003). Connectivity can be estimated for a particular life-stage, such as by tracking animals' movements, over a generation, and by genetic similarities between populations. The latter suggest marine species connectivity is closer to 1000 km than 10 km; with genetic studies indicating connectivity from 315 km to 2,346 km (Manel et al. 2019). Larger individual animals, particularly mammals, fish, turtles and birds, may travel thousands of kilometres every year. Species may also have behaviours to limit their dispersal away from the suitable habitats where their parents lived. Such larval retention mechanisms could be selected for on oceanic islands, for example (Bell, 2008). At least 10 % of marine species have no planktonic larval stage, including some 20,000 peracarid crustaceans, some molluscs and polychaetes (Berkström et al. 2022). However, their global biogeography is similar to that of taxa with planktonic larvae suggesting they disperse as effectively (Arfianti & Costello, 2020).

Climatic connectivity ensures future resilience by accommodating species range shifts driven by climate change. This is often quantified using climate velocity - the speed and direction a species must travel to track its preferred climate conditions as the ocean warms (Burrows et al., 2011, 2019). A network with strong climatic connectivity incorporates these pathways that act as 'stepping-stones' for species range shifts (Fredston-Hermann et al., 2018). In addition to the observed extensions of marine species ranges due to ocean warming cited above, climate resilience can be estimated in several ways. The geographic ranges of species can be modelled for the present and under future climatic conditions such that areas where a species range may contract and expand can be projected. The parts of each species range where it is projected to continue to occur are called climatic macro-refugia. The MPA Europe project has published such models online (Principe et al., 2023) and will map these macro-refugia. At more local scales, climate microrefugia may occur where (a) shading by seagrass, seaweed, rocks reduces heat exposure to seabed life, (b) steep slopes enable mobile species to escape heatwaves by temporarily moving deeper, and (c) localised upwelling of cooler water reduces heatwave impacts (Pinsky et al., 2013; Oliver et al., 2019; Queirós et al., 2021; Dahms & Killen 2023; Benedetti-Cecchi et al., 2024; Kumagi et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2024; Ortiz-Villa et al., 2025). Identifying these local scale microrefugia requires monitoring of temperature at local scales. A third approach involves modelling how ocean currents will transport heat in terms of speed and direction, i.e., climate velocity.

Here, we evaluate how well the proposed MPA network for European seas accommodates both surface ocean current and climatic connectivity using measures of physical connectivity only. To do this, we first model oceanographic connectivity using dispersal simulations based on averaged ocean current data to predict the dispersal of particles at the ocean surface. We then map climate velocity from an ensemble of projected sea surface temperature for mid- and end-of-century scenarios, revealing pathways for species range shifts (Burrows et al., 2014). Using these two layers, we statistically assessed whether how current and climate velocity measures mapped with the high-priority Representative Biodiversity Areas (RBA) proposed by the MPA Europe project. Our analysis tested the hypothesis that the proposed network contains significantly lower connectivity values than non-priority conservation areas (because the algorithm prioritises places with geographically isolated species).

Methods

Study area and spatial framework

The study was conducted across the North Atlantic Ocean and adjacent Baltic, Black and Mediterranean seas, geographically defined by an extent from 35°W to 42.5°E and 25°N to 85°N. The study area was divided into a grid of ocean cells derived from a global 1/12° resolution template, which formed the fundamental nodes for our MPA network analysis. To ensure accurate area-based calculations, all spatial data were standardized to a global Mollweide equal-area projection.

Oceanographic connectivity

We modelled oceanographic connectivity using circuit theory, a flexible and scalable method that translates ocean current velocities into estimates of conductance, representing the ease of passive dispersal between locations (Leonard et al., 2016). Our model incorporates the direction and intensity of currents through an anisotropic function, where conductance between two cells is determined by both the surface current speed and its alignment with the potential dispersal direction (Leonard et al., 2016; Fernández-López & Schliep, 2019).

Oceanographic data was sourced from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) global ocean physics reanalysis product. Specifically, we obtained monthly mean eastward and northward sea water velocity components. The data spanned a 10-year period from January 2010 to December 2020, allowing us to capture long-term oceanographic patterns and variability. For each month in the time series, we calculated current speed and direction to model a monthly conductance matrix representing dispersal potential between adjacent ocean cells. These monthly matrices were then averaged across the entire 10-year period to produce a single, time-averaged conductance matrix. This final matrix represents the 10-year mean potential connectivity throughout the study region.

The time-averaged conductance matrix was used to construct a directed, weighted graph, where each ocean cell is a node and the weighted edges represent the mean conductance between them. To identify cells critical for maintaining network-wide connectivity, we calculated three key centrality metrics:

- (1) *Betweenness Centrality*: To identify crucial "stepping-stone" corridors (Freeman, 1977). Given the graph's large size, we used an approximation algorithm (100,000 samples), providing a computationally efficient measure of how frequently a node lies on the shortest paths between other nodes.
- (2) *Out-strength Centrality*: To identify important dispersal sources. This metric is the sum of conductance values on all outgoing edges from a node, representing its total potential contribution to network-wide dispersal (Tremblay et al., 2008).
- (3) *Harmonic Centrality*: To measure a node's overall accessibility (Marchiori & Latora, 2000). This metric, based on the sum of the reciprocal of shortest-path distances to all other nodes, provides a measure of connectivity that is less sensitive to disconnected components than traditional closeness centrality, which quantifies how close a given node is to all other nodes in a network (i.e., the reciprocal of the average shortest path distance from a node to all other reachable nodes in the graph).

Climatic connectivity

We calculated climate connectivity as climate velocity. The analysis used sea-surface temperature (SST) data from Bio-Oracle 3.0 (Assis et al., 2024), which includes projections from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) earth system models, focusing on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) 3-7.0, a scenario representing a future with high challenges for mitigation and adaptation due to regional rivalries and slower technological development. We compared a baseline period of 2000-2020 with two future 20-year periods: mid-century (2040-2060) and end-of-century (2080-2100).

We calculated climate velocity using established methods that determine the speed and direction of isotherm shifts (Burrows et al., 2014; García Molinos et al., 2019). The velocity is calculated as the ratio of the temporal trend in temperature to the local spatial gradient in temperature. The direction is determined by the local temperature gradients, with positive velocities (warming) pointing towards cooler areas and negative velocities (cooling) towards warmer areas. This gradient-based approach for climate velocity estimation differs from the climate-analogue velocity method (Ordonez & Williams, 2013; Brito-Morales et al., 2018) in tracking shifts in isotherms as a basis for projected distribution shifts rather than estimating the shortest path to the location of the nearest most-similar future climate. A key part of our analysis was the calculation of climate trajectories, which represent the paths that isotherms are expected to follow over time. By classifying the behaviour of these trajectories, we identified key features for climatic connectivity, which may represent climatic corridors for species extending their ranges in response to warming (Burrows et al., 2014). The speed of ocean warming will be greater over mid-ocean areas where there are no upwellings, seabed topography, or other physical factors influencing current movements (Burrows et al., 2019).

Prioritisation scenarios and overlap analysis

We evaluated the spatial congruence between the connectivity metrics and two distinct conservation prioritisation scenarios obtained with the decision-support software Zonation 5 v2.0 using the Core-Area Zonation method (CAZ1) (Lehtomäki & Moilanen 2013; Moilanen *et al.*, 2024). These scenarios represent the top 30% and 10% Representative Biodiversity Areas (RBA) of European seas selected based on two different criteria:

- (1) Run 1, current biodiversity: RBA based on the current distribution of marine species (Figure 1);
- (2) Run 2, current and future biodiversity: RBA also accounting for projected species distribution shifts under the SSP3-7.0 climate scenario.

We defined high connectivity areas as those areas with the top 10% and 30% of their respective connectivity measures. We then overlaid these top 10% and 30% on the top 10% and 30% RBA to see how much of the “high connectivity” occurred with these RBA. We quantified the spatial overlap between the top-tier (10% and 30%) areas of each connectivity metric and each of the two prioritisation scenarios (i.e., Run 1 and Run 2) using two reciprocal metrics:

- (1) Coverage of prioritisation: the proportion of the RBA that is also identified as a high-connectivity area;
- (2) Coverage of connectivity: the proportion of the high-connectivity area that falls within the RBA.

These complementary measures capture how well high-connectivity areas are represented within the RBA and, conversely, how much of the priority areas align with high-connectivity areas.

Because the Zonation algorithm prioritises areas with geographically rare species, we expect the highest priority RBA cells to have low connectivity. To test if the observed overlap exceeded random expectations, we performed a permutation test. We generated 999 null models by randomly selecting ocean cells to match the area of the 10% and 30% RBA. The p-value was calculated as the proportion of null models with an overlap greater than or equal to the observed overlap, providing a statistical measure of significance.

Results

We evaluated the spatial overlap between the 10% and 30% RBA (Figure 1) and the connectivity metrics (Figure 2) on current species distributions (Run 1) and incorporating future projections (Run 2). The results were identical for both Run 1 and Run 2, indicating that the inclusion of future species distributions did not alter the network's overlap with key connectivity areas. This suggests that the changes in sea surface current connectivity in the RBA (i.e., the overall projected ranges of marine species) due to ocean warming will be negligible. Therefore, for simplicity, all subsequent analyses and results are presented for Run 1 only. The climatic and oceanographic connectivity are displayed in Figures 2 & 3.

Oceanographic connectivity

As expected, the congruence between the RBA and ocean current-based connectivity was highly dependent on the protection threshold (Table 1). The larger RBA of 30% had more within RBA connectivity. The prioritised areas captured 26 % of the 'Out-Strength' hotspots and 25 % of the 'Betweenness' hotspots. The reciprocal coverage was similarly high (26 % and 25 %, respectively). 'Harmonic' centrality showed a weaker overlap of approximately 12 % from both perspectives. In contrast, at the 10% protection level, this spatial congruence within the RBA network diminished substantially. The overlap for 'Out-Strength' and 'Betweenness' dropped to 9 % and 7 %, respectively, while 'Harmonic' centrality showed almost no meaningful overlap (~1 %).

A paired Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test confirmed that the centrality values within the identified connectivity metrics were significantly greater than those within the RBA for all metrics ($p < 2.2e-16$). This indicates that while the 10 % and 30 % RBA capture some degree of important connectivity regions, they represent a distinct subset of the overall connectivity landscape. Descriptively, the mean normalised 'Betweenness' centrality across the entire study region was 0.191, compared to a mean of 0.049 within the RBA. Similar patterns were observed for all the region versus within the RBA for: 'out-strength' mean connectivity = 0.050 vs. mean prioritization = 0.014; and harmonic centrality, mean connectivity = 0.123 vs. mean prioritization = 0.010. Permutation tests revealed that the observed overlap for all oceanographic connectivity metrics, at both the 10% and 30% thresholds, was no greater than expected by random chance ($p > 0.999$ for all comparisons).

Climatic connectivity

The analysis revealed a significant spatial mismatch between the RBA (Figure 1) and the hypothesised pathways for climate-driven range shifts (Figure 2A). The 30 % RBA included 10 % of the identified climate velocity putative corridors, while these corridors represented just 2 % of the 30 % RBA. At the stricter 10 % threshold, the overlap became negligible, with only 1.5 % of the putative climate corridors included in the 10 % RBA. As with oceanographic connectivity, permutation tests confirmed that this minimal overlap did not exceed random expectations ($p >$

0.999 for both thresholds). Climate velocity corridors tended to occur through the middle of regional seas (Figure 2: North Sea, Bay of Biscay, Mediterranean) while the RBA was greatest near coasts (Figure 1). This is as expected, as the highest velocities are fastest in open ocean areas, whereas areas of greatest biodiversity are in coastal waters.

Discussion

Our analysis of ocean currents and climate velocity within the RBA found that the congruence was no greater than what would be expected by random chance. However, species also disperse outside the RBA, and many are widely distributed across the MPA Europe study area. Thus, isolated offshore areas in the 10 % and 30 % RBA (Figure 1) are connected by ocean currents (Figure 2). However, the ability of species to utilise these currents varies greatly; some swim as individual animals, but others are unable to traverse these areas due to their short-lived plankton life-stages and sedentary benthic life-stages.

The present mean potential connectivity estimated by ocean current and climate velocity models were limited to surface waters and average conditions. The larger zooplankton of the surface zone, called neuston and including late life-stage decapod larvae, are mostly nocturnal to avoid predation. Vertical movement in the water column is well-established in holoplankton and meroplankton (including eggs). Thus, the role of surface currents in larval dispersal is not known and it is necessary to be cautious in using currents to estimate population connectivity. More direct measures of biological connectivity would be mapping of species ranges, genetic connectivity, and tracking animals' movements. Another approximation is to map benthic habitat connectivity. For example, Sacre et al. (2025) mapped the distribution of seabed habitats in part of the Baltic Sea preferred by more residential fish species (including gobies, bream, minnow, sticklebacks, pike, rudd, tench, carp, perch) that move within 20 km, noting that other species (herring, flounder) function at a sea basin scale. Species' dispersal potential was estimated from observations of juveniles in different habitats and tracking of individual adults, while potential dispersal barriers included dumping and dredging areas, ports and marinas. They could then assess where MPA could best conserve and restore habitats to benefit fish populations.

While most marine species have a planktonic life stage, these vary in duration from minutes to years, and most species are also mobile and able to disperse as adults by swimming, drifting, burrowing and walking (Berkström et al., 2022). A species with a planktonic life-stage may disperse in any direction using the rising, falling and turning of tidal currents, and adjusting its depth to take advantage of counter-currents at different depths. For example, planktonic larvae of sea lice (caligid copepods) and other coastal species can move up into fjords and estuaries and towards the seashore (Costello, 2009). Although surface waters in estuaries move seaward, they sit above a current going the opposite direction. The larvae of the salmon louse stay in mid-depths as nauplii and so move landwards. Once they reach the infective copepodite stage, they swim to the surface during the day to benefit from anabatic winds that transport them towards the seashore and upper estuary where their hosts concentrate. The planktonic larvae of some species of fish and decapods may swim against the current to reach their preferred adult habitat (Berkström et al., 2022). European clawed lobsters are residential, as adults and disperse mainly by their larvae, which are planktonic for 13-35 days and migrate vertically in the water column (potentially avoiding surface currents), such that populations in MPA contribute to adjacent fisheries (Huserbråten et al., 2013). Exceptional weather events and seasonal conditions can also lead to

species colonising areas outside their core range. The best indicator of a species dispersal potential is its realised range. The species used to design the RBA have large ranges and have thus dispersed across areas of varied climatic conditions, indicating that ocean currents at the scale studied here do not limit their dispersal over time. Future analysis of how species ranges may shift under climate warming is needed to assess how well the RBA represents present and future conditions for marine species in European seas.

It is important to acknowledge the methodological considerations that frame our conclusions and point toward future research directions. Our model of oceanographic connectivity, based on circuit theory, provides a powerful proxy for passive larval dispersal but does not account for complex biological factors such as larval behaviour, duration, and mortality, which can influence effective connectivity (Assis et al., 2022; Gouvêa et al., 2023). Similarly, our climatic connectivity analysis relies on SST as the primary driver of climate velocity. While SST is a critical factor, a more holistic assessment would also incorporate other climate stressors like ocean acidification and deoxygenation, as well as non-climatic barriers that could impede species range shifts (Lawlor et al., 2024). Finally, this study evaluated one set of biodiversity prioritisation outputs under a single, high-emissions climate scenario. Future research should build on this foundation by integrating more complex, species-specific biophysical models and exploring network performance under a range of climate scenarios.

The results, by limiting connectivity comparisons to within the RBA, show how important it is that areas outside the RBA do not lose their species so that the MPA become islands of biodiversity. For example, intense seabed dredging and trawling may extirpate species in some areas, as well as releasing carbon into the water. There is also a need to study other indicators of connectivity and climate resilience to develop sufficient understanding to advise policy on MPA planning and management.

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Table 1. Spatial overlap between the RBA 30% and 10%, and the connectivity metrics based on four connectivity measures, which are grouped by climate velocity and ocean currents. "Priority areas" measure the proportion of the RBA area that were also classified as areas of high connectivity, while "Connected areas" measure the proportion of the areas of high connectivity that were captured within the RBA area.

			RBA 10	RBA 30
Climate velocity	Corridor	Priority areas	1.5	10.0
	Corridor	Connected areas	0.8	1.8
Ocean currents	Betweenness	Priority areas	7.0	24.6
	Betweenness	Connected areas	7.1	24.5
	Harmonic	Priority areas	1.0	11.8
	Harmonic	Connected areas	1.0	11.6
	Out-Strength	Priority areas	8.8	25.7
	Out- Strength	Connected areas	8.9	25.7

Figure 1. Conservation prioritization scenarios based on current species distributions with the MPA Europe study area (i.e., EEZ). The maps display the top 10% (top) and 30% (bottom) of marine areas identified as high priority for conservation.

A

B

Figure 2. Maps display the distribution of two of the four different connectivity metrics within the MPA Europe study area: (A) climate velocity corridors and (B) out-strength centrality, sources of dispersal. Maps are scaled from less (yellow) to more (red).

C

D

Figure 3. Maps display the distribution of two of the four different connectivity metrics within the MPA Europe study area: (C) between-ness centrality, stepping stones, and (D) harmonic centrality, more accessible areas. Maps are scaled from less (yellow) to more (red).

